

The place of environmental education in the family

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Annotation: This article highlights the place of environmental education in the family. The authors of the article believe that the spiritual and physical life of a person at all its stages of development is inextricably linked with nature. The main goal of environmental education in a modern family is to form a culture of behavior and social responsibility of their children for nature, which in turn is itself an inexhaustible source of education through its diversity and beauty. It is the beauty of nature in any corner of our planet where a person lives that gives rise to a feeling of love for his Homeland, his home, mother, and people. Man stands at the highest stage of the development of life on earth, but this does not mean that all nature belongs to him, as he arrogantly imagines. Man belongs to nature. He must understand this, learn how to use her wealth rationally and protect her incomparable beauty. **Keywords:** environmental education, formation, culture, feeling, social, responsibility, source, beauty, nature, rationally, diversity.

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INTRODUCTION

Most of a person's life is spent in the family. For each of its members, it is a certain living space, an entire ecological microsystem in which everyone strives to realize themselves and at the same time is in close contact with all family members.

The child is born completely helpless. Parents begin to teach their tiny creature to live in the world around them. Every year the world of children expands and becomes more diverse. This is not only the house in which the child lives, it is a courtyard, garden, park, city, village, river, field, i.e. the habitat of people.

How will the child behave in the world around him? It largely depends on us, adults, on environmental education in the family. The main goal of environmental education in a modern family is to form a culture of behavior and social responsibility of their children for nature, which in turn is itself an inexhaustible source of education through its diversity and beauty. It is the beauty of nature in any corner of our planet where a person lives that gives rise to a feeling of love for his Homeland, his home, mother, and people.

In order to carry out the process of environmental education in a family environment, parents can: read various encyclopedias about wildlife, look at book illustrations with children, show educational films about animal life, read fiction about nature (stories by Prishvin, Bianchi, Ushinsky), take care of indoor plants with a child, take joint walks in the forest, park to watch the habits of birds and insects on the river.

It is available to everyone to plant a blooming garden in their room on the windowsill or in special stands. This is the comfort of the house. Flowers create a special atmosphere of peace and celebration. And this is the fertile environment that educates children and protects their health. The beauty of the surrounding world helps to develop a child's aesthetic taste, fosters love and respect for nature.

Such people will create garden cities, green courtyards, streets, villages. They will not raise their hand to break a green branch with clusters of scarlet berries or uproot a young tree. They will stop those who try to shoot down a bird with a slingshot or tear apart a bright spring butterfly that flutters merrily over flowers in squares and parks, they will protect nature and man himself.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

From the very first steps, it is necessary to put into the child's mind the concept that the spiritual and physical life of a person at all its stages of development is inextricably linked with nature. Scientists claim that living organisms grow faster if music is played around them. They also claim that it has a calming effect on people and causes joy in communicating with animals: cats, dogs, hamsters, turtles, etc.

Man stands at the highest stage of the development of life on earth, but this does not mean that all nature belongs to him, as he arrogantly imagines. Man belongs to nature. He must understand this, learn how to use her wealth rationally and protect her incomparable beauty.

In the concept of environmental education, the family should help the child to form a culture of behavior in his environment, the family should convey to the child that it is a person, even a small one, who is directly responsible for nature and the environment. The family should instill in the child a love of nature, parents help children understand the aesthetics of the world around them. People should preserve nature not only for themselves, but also for posterity. Educating young people about the need to protect nature is a responsible task for adults.

According to the definition of F. According to Engels, given in the book "The Origin of the Family, Private Property and the State", the family is a small group based on marriage or consanguinity, whose members are connected by common life, mutual moral responsibility and mutual assistance.

In the history of the family, L.G. Morgan, in his book "Ancient Society or a study of the lines of human progress from savagery through barbarism to civilization," identified the following historical stages in the evolution of the family and marriage. Promiscuity is promiscuous sexual intercourse between primitive men and women. A blood-related family is the first stage of a family based on a group marriage between brothers and sisters of two clans. The punalua family is based on the group marriage of several sisters, relatives and relatives (cousins and second cousins), with the husbands of each of them. A paired family is the formation of permanent couples for a more or less long period, but without the exception of cohabitation. Both a woman and a man can have several husbands and wives. A monogamous family is the lifelong monogamy of individual couples with the exception of cohabitation. The origin and inheritance are established by the paternal line. In recent decades, a married family has emerged, dominated by equal relations, the stability of marriage depends on the desires and quality of the relationship between the spouses.

The desire for family happiness and family well-being finds expression in the creation of family traditions. Family traditions are what people adhere to in the circle of their family, no matter what size it is. They can be expressed in customs, things, celebrations of memorable dates and much more.

Family traditions should be based not only on blood and kinship ties, but also on the upbringing of children in the spirit of respect for the environment and in the spirit of nature conservation.

According to the majority of scientists (S.N. Glazachev, V.A. Ignatova, G.P. Sikorskaya), environmental education should be understood as a continuous process of education and upbringing aimed at mastering systematic knowledge about the environment, environmental skills, and the formation of a common environmental culture.

From our point of view, the purpose of environmental education in the family should be the formation of family members' attitude to the world around them, which provides a conscious desire to acquire the knowledge, skills and abilities necessary for

the personal participation of each family member in solving and preventing environmental problems, reducing anthropogenic impact on the environment. The formation of the foundations for understanding the unity and interconnection of man and the world around him, the education of the principles of interaction with the outside world are also significant tasks of environmental education.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Researchers, including I.V. Bulygina, identify the following areas of environmental education in the family:

- teaching children the skills of caring for their own homes, domestic and agricultural animals, indoor plants;
- teaching children about the careful use of water, electricity, and food;
- formation of a culture of consumption and understanding among family members of the need for recycling of household waste;
- organization of educational activities among children and their parents in informal associations at institutions and home administrations.

We explain the special attention to the problems of environmental education of children by two main reasons:

- the need to consider environmental education as a continuous and systematic process throughout the active period of life;
 - the relevance of the formation of an elementary ecological culture in the most favorable period of the child's emotional interaction with nature.
- From our point of view, environmental education is the formation of unity of consciousness and behavior in harmony with nature. The beauty of the surrounding world helps to develop a child's aesthetic taste, fosters love and respect for nature.

We assume that environmental education will be successful if adult family members themselves possess knowledge about the natural environment, demonstrate prudent management of the Land (in their yard, on a garden plot, etc.); by their example, they affirm a healthy lifestyle and demonstrate ethical norms of behavior in nature; family traditions are used (a child was born-plant a tree, getting to know the life of nature at different times of the year during family hikes and during family vacations, etc.).

Based on the analysis of accumulated statistical materials on the problem of formation of ecological culture, we have identified indicators of ecological culture:

- knowledge (about nature, relationships in nature, ways of rational use, conservation and enhancement);
- interests (in nature, in the problems of its protection);
- feelings towards nature (moral and aesthetic);
- motives that determine actions in relation to nature;
- positive activity and behavior in nature.

To the question: "At what age should a child be taught to take care of nature?" - the majority of respondents answered that from the age of five and older. There were no respondents who answered in the column "Their own figure" - from the moment of birth. And the basic principle of education says that teach the child while it lies across the bench.

To the question: "Were you taught to take care of the surrounding nature in childhood?" - most of the respondents replied that they had been taught. There were no people among the respondents who would answer this question negatively. There were respondents who did not remember this phenomenon.

There is no question: "Who, in your opinion, should be involved in the education of a child?" - the majority of respondents came to the opinion that parents should do this.

The degree of familiarity of respondents with modern environmental problems (what is the current environmental situation in the world; the problem of waste, etc.) was revealed in the process of studying the results of the survey on these aspects. It turned out that the majority of respondents do not have a clear enough understanding of them. The results of the survey on the need for environmental education of children in the family turned out to be interesting. All respondents agreed that environmental education in the family is necessary, but for this it is necessary to increase the environmental literacy of the parents themselves.

The respondents made the following suggestions to improve the environmental situation in the world:

- conducting public agitation in order to improve environmental culture,
- introduction of penalties,
- transition to waste-free production,
- the use of new energy sources,
- reduction of greenhouse gas emissions into the atmosphere due to innovative technologies in production (use of electric arc furnaces in steel production),
- increasing the number of dumpsters,
- sorting of garbage,
- ...and much more.

CONCLUSION

Currently, very little attention is paid to environmental education and upbringing. If the level of ecological culture of the planet's population becomes higher, this will lead to a change in the state of the environment, which in turn will entail the "purification" of our planet from garbage that has accumulated for a very long time. And if we add waste-free production and recycling of existing waste to everything else, then the situation in the world will begin to change for the better. Our future depends on our children, and they depend on us. It is our duty to pay more attention to environmental education, because the formation of a child's worldview develops from the first days of his life, and parents can give him this knowledge from birth.

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